

Quantum Mechanics is EPR-complete and the Bell inequalities do not hold

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Abstract

We show that time translation in Quantum Mechanics is a stochastic process if and only if it is deterministic. More generally, we show that there is a group action of a Wigner's symmetry group on the probability distribution for the state of a system, if and only if the Wigner's symmetry group transforms deterministic (probability) distributions into deterministic (probability) distributions. This fact is overlooked by the assumptions of both the Bell's theorem and the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen (EPR) paradox.

Taking this fact into account, we show that 1) Quantum Mechanics is a complete statistical theory (as defined by EPR, e.g. like thermodynamics), thus the Bell inequalities do not hold (since Quantum Mechanics cannot be distinguished from a complete statistical theory); 2) any deterministic theory compatible with the predictions of relativistic Quantum Mechanics necessarily respects relativistic causality; 3) at least one deterministic theory compatible with the predictions of relativistic Quantum Mechanics exists, and we build such deterministic theory explicitly using a pseudorandom number generator.

one might have expected that actually producing biased science would have a stronger influence on public opinion than merely sharing others' results. But when one compares the two treatments we consider above, there are strong senses in which the less invasive, more subtle strategy of selective sharing is more effective than biased production, all things considered, particularly when the scientific community is large and the problem at hand is difficult (or the power of generic experiments is low). The reason is that such a scientific community will produce, on its own, plenty of research that, taken without proper context, lends credence to falsehoods.

[...] Industrial selection involves identifying methods already present among the community of scientists that tend to favor one's preferred outcome, and then funding scientists who already use those methods.

[...] by increasing the number of ambient industry-favorable results in a scientific literature, and then further amplifying those results by sharing them selectively, propagandists can have an even stronger effect.

[...] there is little incentive, and often few resources, for individual scientists produce consistently high quality studies. And as we have seen, low powered studies are more likely to spuriously support erroneous conclusions.

[...] the regular publication and acceptance of ultimately incorrect results is certainly troubling. But the arguments and results we have given here suggest that even more is at stake: the same sorts of conditions that lead to a replication crisis in the first place also provide extra fodder for industrial propaganda.

— J. Weatherall and C. O'Connor and J. Bruner (2018) [1]

It is a fundamental doctrine of quantum information science that quantum communication and quantum computation outperforms their classical counterparts. If this is to be true, some fundamental quantum characteristics must be behind better-than-classical performance of information processing tasks.

[...] it will be demonstrated how quantum contextuality and violations of local realism can be used as useful resources in quantum information applications.

— M. Żukowski and Č. Brukner (2012) [2]

One could object to this conclusion on the grounds that our criterion of reality is not sufficiently restrictive. Indeed, one would not arrive at our conclusion if one insisted that two or more physical quantities can be regarded as simultaneous elements of reality only when they can be simultaneously measured or predicted. On this point of view, since either one or the other, but not both simultaneously, of the quantities P and Q can be predicted, they are not simultaneously real. This makes the reality of P and Q depend upon the process of measurement carried out on the first system, which does not disturb the second system in any way. No reasonable definition of reality could be expected to permit this.

— Einstein and Podolsky and Rosen (1935) [3]

1 Introduction

The Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen (EPR) main claim [3] (namely, that Quantum Mechanics is an incomplete description of physical reality), is defended by reducing to absurd the negation of the main claim, i.e. by reducing to absurd that position (Q) and momentum (P) are not

simultaneous elements of reality. In the EPR article it is stated: “*one would not arrive at our conclusion if one insisted that two or more physical quantities can be regarded as simultaneous elements of reality only when they can be simultaneously measured or predicted.[...] This makes the reality of P and Q depend upon the process of measurement carried out on the first system, which does not disturb the second system in any way. No reasonable definition of reality could be expected to permit this.*”

The reduction to absurd of the negation of the claim, could only be a satisfactory argument if the claim itself (namely, the quantities position and momentum of the same particle are simultaneous elements of reality, despite they cannot be simultaneously measured or predicted) would not be absurd as well. But the claim itself raises eyebrows to say the least, once we remember that (in Quantum Mechanics, by definition) measuring the position with infinite precision completely erases any knowledge about the momentum of the same particle.

Moreover, in Quantum Mechanics any sequence of measurements is a Markov stochastic process¹. Note that any non-Markov stochastic process can be described as a Markov stochastic process where some variables defining the state of the system are hidden (i.e. unknown) [5, 6].

Thus position and momentum may be simultaneous elements of reality, but only in another theory very different from Quantum Mechanics. That both the claim and its negation are absurd, is strong evidence that some of the assumptions leading to the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen (EPR) paradox [3] do not hold.

In this paper we will show that one fact was overlooked by the assumptions of the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen (EPR) article: time translation in Quantum Mechanics is a stochastic process if and only if it is deterministic. More generally, we show that there is a group action of a Wigner’s symmetry group on the probability distribution for the state of a system if and only if the Wigner’s symmetry group transforms deterministic (probability) distributions into deterministic (probability) distributions.

Unlike many popular no-go arguments [7], we are not arguing against the requirement that a physical theory should be complete, in fact we will show that Quantum Mechanics is a complete statistical theory (as defined by EPR). Thus the Bell inequalities [8] do not hold—since Quantum Mechanics cannot be distinguished from a complete statistical theory—and the above mathematical fact was also overlooked by the assumptions of the Bell inequalities.

Note that Bohr already declared Quantum Mechanics as a “complete” theory, however he did it at the cost of a radical revision of the classical notions of causality and physical reality [9]. He wrote: “Indeed the finite interaction between object and measuring agencies conditioned by the very existence of the quantum of action entails —because of the impossibility of controlling the reaction of the object on the measuring instruments if these are to serve their purpose— the necessity of a final renunciation of the classical ideal of causality and a radical revision of our attitude towards the problem of physical reality.” [9] Such notion of a “complete” theory

¹The term (non-)Markov stochastic process is used in this paper in the classical sense as in reference [4]. We do not mean a quantum (non-)Markov stochastic process as in reference [4], despite the fact that Quantum Mechanics is used to calculate the transition probabilities between measurements.

mostly favours the EPR claim: the only way that Quantum Mechanics could be complete is if it is incompatible with the classical notions of causality and physical reality. Thus from a logic point of view, there is no disagreement between Einstein and Bohr, their disagreement is about what basic features an acceptable theory should have, whether or not it should be compatible with the classical notions of causality and physical reality.

In contrast, the fact stated above which was overlooked is perfectly compatible with the classical notions of causality and physical reality, as we will show in this paper. We claim that Quantum Mechanics—being non-deterministic and thus a generalization of classical mechanics—does not entail a radical departure from the basic features that an acceptable theory should have, according to EPR [3]. In fact in Quantum Mechanics and in classical Hamiltonian mechanics, the state of an individual system is a point in a phase space, and the phase space is both the domain and image of the deterministic physical transformations.

In the proof of the overlooked fact, we use Wigner’s theorem [10, 11], which determines how a symmetry group acts on a wave-function. We discuss in Section 2 how to relate a wave-function with an arbitrary probability distribution.

Note that in this paper, the Hilbert space is always considered to be a separable Hilbert space [12] and unless otherwise stated it is a real Hilbert space.

2 Wave-function parametrization

Often quantum mechanics is interpreted as providing the probabilities of transition between different states of an individual system. This transition happens upon measurement, any measurement. The state of the system is defined by the wave-function which collapses to a different wave-function upon measurement. This raises a number of interpretation problems as to what do we mean by state of a system. If the state before measurement is A, but the state after measurement is B, what is then the state during the measurement: A and/or B or something else?

The ensemble interpretation of Quantum Mechanics [13, 14] avoids these interpretation problems: the state of the ensemble is unambiguously the probability distribution for the states of an individual system—as in statistical physics². The state of an individual system is a point in a phase space. The possible states of the ensemble are related by physical transformations. For instance, a translation in space-time or a rotation may change the state of the ensemble.

However, the ensemble interpretation does not address the question why the wave-function plays a central role in the calculation of the probability distribution, unlike most other interpretations of quantum mechanics. By being compatible with most (if not all) interpretations of Quantum Mechanics, the ensemble interpretation is in practise a common denominator of most interpretations of Quantum Mechanics. It is useful, but it is not enough. For instance, the ensemble interpretation does not give any explanation as to why it looks like the electron’s

²Note that the notion of probability distribution is not free from interpretation problems [15], but we believe these are intrinsic to any application of statistics.

wave-function interferes with itself in the double-slit experiment—that would imply that the wave-function describes (at least partially) an individual system. Moreover, the most prominent advocates of the ensemble interpretation were dissatisfied with the complementarity of position and momentum [3, 16], convincing themselves and others that the complementarity of position and momentum could not be satisfactorily explained by the the ensemble interpretation alone.

This status changed recently, as it was shown by the present author [17] that the wave-function is merely one possible parametrization of any probability distribution. The parametrization is a surjective map from an hypersphere to the set of all possible probability distributions. The fact that the hypersphere is a surface of constant radius reflects the fact that the integral of the probability distribution is always 1. Two wave-functions are always related by a rotation of the hypersphere, which is a linear transformation and it preserves the hypersphere. It is thus a good parametrization which allows us to represent a group of transformations using linear transformations of the hypersphere, including for stochastic processes which are not Markov processes. The wave-function can be described as a multi-dimensional generalization of Euler’s formula, and its collapse as a generalization of taking the real part of Euler’s formula.

The fact that the wave-function parametrizes any probability distribution means that the wave-function collapse is a feature of all random phenomena. Thus the wave-function collapse is not provoked by the interaction with the environment³; the wave-function collapse does not emerge from some particular cases of classical statistics [20]; Quantum Mechanics is *not* a generalization of the concept of probability algebra from commutative to non-commutative algebra [21]; and thus quantum computation/information is not fundamentally different from classical computation/information⁴. The wave-function is a possible parametrization for any theory of Statistics, including Statistical Physics.

This is comforting, since it is consistent with the empirical facts that Quantum Mechanics applies to a very wide range of physical systems, from the Hydrogen atom, a neutron star or the Universe; and that the collapse occurs upon measurement, any measurement. This also opens the door into applying the wave-function parametrization not just to quantum mechanics, but also to quantum statistical mechanics or even to other problems involving statistics other than quantum physics [23]. For instance, sequential systems are a framework for machine learning that shares several features with Quantum Mechanics [24–26], (more) application of quantum methods to sequential systems thus seems straightforward. Other applications of quantum methods in statistics, either did not use the wave-function parametrization⁵; or they considered

³In a measurement there is always an interaction with the environment, therefore the environment necessarily affects the ensemble and it is possible that decoherence occurs. But such phenomena will be accounted for by the dependence of the ensemble from physical transformations. Note that a continuous (repeated) quantum measurement is a model of decoherence and thus decoherence does not avoid by itself the wave-function collapse [18, 19]. In case we opt for a model of decoherence which avoids collapse, then we are necessarily dealing with an alternative to Quantum Mechanics, such case was discussed above.

⁴Different computers always have different properties, for instance different logic gates may enhance the performance of different algorithms [22]. But neglecting performance, the quantum bits can be constructed using classical bits and quantum logic gates can also be constructed using classical logic gates, with the Hadamard transform as an example.

⁵Analogies with the wave-function were made but unitarity was not preserved [27–30]

only deterministic scenarios [31, 32].

3 Comparing the time evolution with a stochastic process

Quantum Mechanics is not a generalization of probability theory, but it is definitely a generalization of classical mechanics since it involves non-deterministic transformations to the state of the system. For instance, the time evolution may be non-deterministic unlike in classical mechanics.

There are three major metaphysical views of time [33]: presentism, eternalism and possibilism. The possibilism consists in considering the presentism for the future and the eternalism for the past, so it is inconsistent with a time translation symmetry. The presentism view coincides with the Hamiltonian formalism of physics, that the state of the system is defined by a point in the phase space. When the time evolution of the system is deterministic it traces a phase space trajectory for the system, however the definition of the state of the system does not involve time, i.e. only the present exists ⁶. The eternalism view coincides with the Lagrangian formalism of physics, that the state of the system is defined by a function of time. When the time evolution of the system is deterministic, this function of time coincides with the phase-space trajectory of the Hamiltonian formalism and so which metaphysical view of time we use is irrelevant from an experimental point of view (in the deterministic case).

But when the time evolution of the system is non-deterministic, we may have a hard time studying the time evolution from the Lagrangian formalism and/or eternalism metaphysical view. The key fact about Quantum Mechanics which makes it incompatible with the eternalism/Lagrangian point of view is that the time evolution is not necessarily a stochastic process, i.e. there is not necessarily a collection of random events indexed by time. We only apply one non-deterministic transformation of the state of the system, however there are many different transformations we can choose from and the set of choices is indexed by a parameter we call time, which is fine from the presentism/Hamiltonian point of view since only the present exists.

Note that a random experiment always involves a preparation followed by a measurement. For instance, we shake a dice in our hand and throw it to a table until it stops (preparation), then we check the position where it stopped (measurement).

If we just throw the dice without shaking our hand, the probability distribution for the measurement outcome is different than if we shake our hand. There is nothing mysterious about this: two different preparations lead to two different probability distributions; this is effectively the case of two different theories leading to two different predictions. Whether or not we actually do the measurement does not change anything, what changes the probability distribution is the preparation.

Then we can think about a preparation which is function of an element of a symmetry group,

⁶The presentism view is fully compatible with (non-quantum) special or general relativity[34, 35]. There are difficulties with the quantum versions of relativity (more with general relativity than with special relativity [36]), but these difficulties have little to do with the presentism as we will discuss in forthcoming articles.

for instance translation in time. From the point of view of probability theory or experimental physics, this is a valid option. However, it is important to note that this preparation function of time is not a stochastic process in time. A stochastic process in time is a set of random experiments indexed by time, while in the preparation which is function of time we have a single random experiment dependent on the parameter time. As an example, consider a) throwing the dice 10 times, one time per minute during 10 minutes and b) shake the dice in our hand for a number of minutes T between 0 and 10 and then throw the dice once. The preparation in b) is dependent on the time parameter T , while in a) the time selects the one of the many identically prepared experiments which was done at the selected time.

Note that the experiments a) and b) above are different but can be combined: we could do many random experiments, each of them would be dependent on a parameter. This fact is important in the next section.

4 Deterministic transformations

The relation between quantum mechanics and a statistical theory (both are non-deterministic) is clear: the wave-function is a parametrization for any probability distribution [17]. The representation of a symmetry group is always linear and unitary [10, 11]. This does not exclude deterministic representations, however the deterministic representations are usually not irreducible [36] so they are not the building blocks of the theory.

Theories such as classical electrodynamics or more generally classical non-abelian gauge theories [37] involve a system of non-linear partial differential equations. It is a very hard problem to study in general the space of classical solutions of such systems⁷. Even when a few solutions can be found, they may not be the ones that describe the physical system correctly. A consistent theory covering many cases only exists (at the moment) for systems of linear partial differential equations [39]. Thus to solve many non-linear deterministic theories we may not have better alternative (at the moment) than to consider them as a particular case of a statistical theory and apply linear quantum methods on its wave-function parametrization [31, 40]—then the building blocks of the overall deterministic theory are non-deterministic.

A deterministic transformation acts as $E(P_A) \rightarrow E(P_B)$ where A, B are events, for any probability distribution E and event A . When the probability is concentrated in the neighborhood of a single outcome (say A), we have effectively a deterministic case and this transformation ($A \rightarrow B$) conserves the determinism, thus it is a deterministic transformation.

Note that above, P_A and P_B necessarily commute. On the other hand, if the transformation is such that $E(P_A) \rightarrow E(UP_AU^\dagger)$ where P_B and UP_AU^\dagger do not commute for some events A, B , then the transformation cannot be deterministic. Consider the discrete case with $E(P_n)$ given by $Tr(P_mP_n) = \delta_{mn}$ up to a normalization factor, for instance. Then $Tr(P_mP_n) \rightarrow Tr(P_mUP_nU^\dagger) = U_{nm}^2$. If the transformation would be deterministic, then necessarily $U_{nm}^2 =$

⁷A well known example is the Navier-Stokes equation [38].

δ_{kn} for some $k = f(n)$ dependent on n , and so $UP_nU^\dagger = P_l$ with $l = f^{-1}(n)$ would commute with P_r for any indexes r and n .

We get to the conclusion that a transformation U is deterministic if and only if P_A and UP_BU^\dagger commute for all events A, B . Thus, the complementarity of two observables (e.g. position and momentum) is due to the random nature of the physical transformation relating the two observables. This clarifies that probability theory has no trouble in dealing with non-commuting observables, as long as the collapse of the wave-function occurs.

5 Time translation is a stochastic process if and only if it is deterministic

Now we are able to prove the main result of this paper, namely that there is a group action of a Wigner's symmetry group on the probability distribution for the state of a system, if and only if the Wigner's symmetry group transforms deterministic (probability) distributions into deterministic (probability) distributions. A corollary is that time translation in Quantum Mechanics is a stochastic process if and only if it is deterministic. This mathematical fact is overlooked by the assumptions of both the Bell's theorem and the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen (EPR) paradox.

As it was discussed in reference [17], Wigner's theorem [10, 11] implies that the action of a symmetry group on the wave-function is necessarily linear and unitary.

As we have seen in the previous section, the action of a symmetry group on the wave-function is deterministic if and only if P_A and $U_gP_BU_g^\dagger$ commute for all events A, B and for all the elements g of the group, where P_A is a projection-valued-measure.

This means that U is a deterministic transformation if and only if $U_{la}U_{ma}^* = 0$ for all a, l, m such that $l \neq m$.

Now we check the necessary and sufficient conditions for the action of a symmetry group on the wave-function to correspond to an action on the corresponding probability distribution.

That is, if we start with some probability distribution $\text{diag}(\rho_1)$, then the action of each element g of the group on the wave-function will produce (after the collapse) a different probability distribution $\text{diag}(\rho_g)$. The composition of the actions of two group elements g, h on the probability distribution is given by the succession of the two random experiments corresponding to g and h : $P(A) = \text{tr}(\text{diag}(\rho_g)U_hP_AU_h^\dagger)$.

However, Wigner's theorem [10, 11] implies that the action of a symmetry group on the wave-function is necessarily linear and unitary, thus $P(A) = \text{tr}(\rho_gU_hP_AU_h^\dagger)$.

Thus there is a group action of the symmetry group on the probability distribution if and only if $\text{tr}(\text{diag}(\rho_g)U_hP_AU_h^\dagger) = \text{tr}(\rho_gU_hP_AU_h^\dagger)$ for any pure density matrix ρ_g and any event A and group element h .

The equality above is equivalent to $\sum_{k,b:k \neq b} U_{ka}^* \Psi_k \Psi_b^* U_{ba} = 0$, where U_{ba} are the elements of the matrix U_h . We can see that if U is a deterministic transformation, then the equality

is satisfied, since $U_{ja}^* U_{jl} = 0$ for all a, l, j such that $a \neq l$. On the other hand, if U is a non-deterministic transformation then for some a, l, m such that $l \neq m$, we have $U_{ma}^* U_{la} \neq 0$. Then for $\Psi_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\delta_{km} + \delta_{kl})$, then we get $\sum_{k,b:k \neq b} U_{ka}^* \Psi_k \Psi_b^* U_{ba} = U_{ma}^* U_{la} \neq 0$, i.e. there is no group action of the symmetry group on the probability distribution.

6 Quantum Mechanics is a complete statistical theory

In Quantum Mechanics as in classical Hamiltonian mechanics, the state of an individual system is a point in a phase space, and the phase space is both the domain and image of the deterministic physical transformations. As in any statistical theory, we may know only the probability distribution for the state of the individual system, instead of knowing the state of the individual system. The relation between quantum mechanics and a statistical theory is clear: the wave-function is a parametrization for any probability distribution [17].

There are two kinds of incompleteness in a non-Markov stochastic process. The two kinds of incompleteness are in correspondence with the two concepts: stochastic and non-Markov, respectively.

1) Stochastic: From the point of view of (classical) information theory [41], the root of probabilities (i.e. non-determinism) is by definition the absence of information. Statistical methods are required whenever we lack complete information about a system, as so often occurs when the system is complex [23]. Thus we can convert a deterministic process to a stochastic process unambiguously (using trivial probability distributions); but we cannot convert a stochastic process into a deterministic process unambiguously since we need new information ⁸.

2) non-Markov: any non-Markov stochastic process can be described as a Markov stochastic process where some variables defining the state of the system are hidden (i.e. unknown) [5, 6]. Conversely, by definition any irreducible ⁹ Markov process where some variables defining the state of the system are hidden will give rise to a non-Markov process. For instance, the physical phenomena which generates examples of brownian motion is deterministic and thus Markov, but real-world brownian motion is often non-Markov (because we cannot measure the state of the system completely [43, 44]) despite the fact that the brownian motion is one of the most famous examples of a Markov process.

In reference [45] (authored by A. Einstein and contemporary of the EPR paradox) the two kinds of incompleteness are clearly distinguished:

“[...] *I believe that the [quantum] theory is apt to beguile us into error in our search for a uniform basis for physics, because, in my belief, it is an incomplete representation of real things, although it is the only one which can be built out of the fundamental concepts of force and material points (quantum corrections to classical mechanics). The incompleteness of the*

⁸E.g. the assumptions required by the deterministic models in reference [42] are new information.

⁹The word irreducible avoids the case where the state of the system is the direct product of two states corresponding to 2 irreducible Markov processes, in such case the fact that some variables are hidden does not imply that the resulting stochastic process is non-Markov.

representation is the outcome of the statistical nature (incompleteness) of the laws. I will now justify this opinion.”

The incompleteness of the representation corresponds to the non-Markov kind, while the incompleteness of the laws corresponds to the stochastic kind. By definition, Quantum Mechanics is stochastic (thus it has the stochastic kind of incompleteness). But as we discussed in the beginning of our article, it would be absurd to consider that Quantum Mechanics has the non-Markov kind of incompleteness since a sequence of measurements in Quantum Mechanics is a Markov stochastic process.

So, why did the author tried to justify (using the EPR paradox [3], among other arguments) that in Quantum Mechanics the stochastic kind of incompleteness necessarily leads to a non-Markov kind of incompleteness?

The following paragraph from the same reference [45] suggests that the author was trying to favor the cause that any future theoretical basis should be deterministic, not just Markov (since statistical mechanics is often Markov).

“There is no doubt that quantum mechanics has seized hold of a beautiful element of truth, and that it will be a test stone for any future theoretical basis, in that it must be deducible as a limiting case from that basis, just as electrostatics is deducible from the Maxwell equations of the electromagnetic field or as thermodynamics is deducible from classical mechanics. However, I do not believe that quantum mechanics will be the starting point in the search for this basis, just as, vice versa, one could not go from thermodynamics (resp. statistical mechanics) to the foundations of mechanics.”

However and as discussed in Section 4, there is no mathematical argument that suggests that in general a deterministic model is more fundamental than a stochastic one, quite the opposite. Since the wave-function is merely a possible parametrization of any probability distribution [17], we also cannot claim that a deterministic model is more fundamental than Quantum Mechanics. Thus, the stochastic kind of incompleteness is harmless.

So, the EPR paradox appears as an attempt to justify a mathematical statement (that a deterministic model is more fundamental than Quantum Mechanics) with arguments from physics (trying to link to the non-Markov kind of incompleteness), for which no mathematical arguments could be found. Note that a statement referring to any future theoretical basis is essentially a mathematical statement because the physical model is any (since the theoretical basis is any).

However, it is a failed attempt because it missed the fact discussed in the previous section, that the time evolution is a stochastic process if and only if it is deterministic. In the EPR paradox, there is no probability distribution for the state of system after the spatial separation of the entangled particles and before the transformation involved in the measurement takes place, because the time evolution (being in this case non-deterministic) is not a stochastic process. We can only consider the probability distribution for the state of system after the spatial separation of the entangled particles and after the transformation involved in the measurement takes place.

This is overall a non-local physical transformation since it involves the spatial separation of the entangled particles. But it does not violate relativistic causality, since both the spatial separation of the entangled particles and the transformation involved in the measurement do not by themselves violate relativistic causality, so their composition does not violate causality either.

The Bell inequalities [8] do not hold either—since Quantum Mechanics cannot be distinguished from a complete statistical theory—and that the time evolution is a stochastic process if and only if it is deterministic was also overlooked by the assumptions of the Bell inequalities.

7 Any deterministic theory compatible with relativistic Quantum Mechanics necessarily respects relativistic causality

The only known theory consistent with the experimental results in high energy physics [46] is a quantum gauge field theory which is mathematically ill-defined [47]. Due to the mathematical illness, the relation of such a theory with Quantum Mechanics is still object of debate and it will be addressed soon in another article by the present author.

In the mean time we will have to consider a free system, which suffices to address the EPR paradox. For a free system, we know well what is relativistic Quantum Mechanics [48]. The time evolution of the wave-function is described by the Dirac equation for a free particle, which is a real (i.e. non-complex) equation.

Relativistic causality is satisfied in relativistic Quantum Mechanics, meaning that there is a propagator which vanishes for a space-like propagation [48]. In other words, the probability that the system moves faster than light is null.

A deterministic theory compatible with relativistic Quantum Mechanics is one which when applied to an ensemble of free systems, will reproduce the statistical predictions of Quantum Mechanics.

Since in relativistic Quantum Mechanics the probability that the system moves faster than light is null, then no system (described by the deterministic theory) in the ensemble moves faster than light. Thus any deterministic theory compatible with relativistic Quantum Mechanics necessarily respects relativistic causality. The question we left open here and address in the next section, is whether one such deterministic theory exists.

8 A deterministic theory compatible with relativistic Quantum Mechanics

Does a deterministic theory—consistent with the non-deterministic time evolution of Quantum Mechanics—exists?

The answer is yes, and we will build one example of such deterministic theory in this section.

In an experimental setting, we always have a discrete set of possible outcomes and thus Quantum Mechanics always predicts a cumulative distribution function. This allows us to apply the inverse-transform sampling method [49] for generating pseudo-random numbers consistently with the probability distribution predicted by Quantum Mechanics.

An experiment in Quantum mechanics always involves the repetition of an experimental procedure many times. In the deterministic theory however, each time we execute the experimental procedure we are not executing exactly the same experimental procedure. We consider a number (any number will do) which will be the seed of the pseudo-random number generator and then we generate pseudo-random numbers consistently with the probability distribution predicted by Quantum Mechanics. The experimental procedure is: 1) generate one pseudo-random number and 2) modify the state of the system accordingly with the pseudo-random number.

In the case of relativistic Quantum Mechanics, the probability of violating relativistic causality is null. Thus, the experimental procedure never violates relativistic causality. The modifications of the state of the system are however necessarily not infinitesimal since the phase space of the experimental setting is discrete. This does not violate relativistic causality, since the finite modifications to the state of the system occur in finite intervals of time.

We can however consider intervals of time as small as we like and thus modifications to the state of the system as small as we like. The only requirement for this is that the computational resources involved in the pseudo-random number generation are as large as needed (which is valid from a logical point of view). Note that since time evolution in quantum mechanics is not necessarily a stochastic process, we will often have that a sequence of experimental procedures executed at regular and small intervals of time produces different statistical data than just one experimental procedure executed at once after the same total time has passed (e.g. in the double-slit experiment). But this cannot be considered a radical departure of the classical notion of physical reality, since in the (very old) presentism view of classical Hamiltonian mechanics, the phase space (i.e. the physical reality) does not involve the notion of time [33]. Moreover when the time evolution is deterministic then it is a stochastic process, therefore if we study only deterministic transformations then we can recover the eternalism view of classical Lagrangian mechanics without any conflict with relativistic causality. For instance, this implies that in the double-slit experiment we can in principle reconstruct the trajectory of each particle and conclude about which slit the particle has went through.

From a logical point of view, this deterministic theory is valid and by definition it always agrees with the experimental predictions of Quantum Mechanics, thus it is experimentally indistinguishable from Quantum Mechanics.

From the metaphysics point of view, this deterministic theory is unacceptable, since it involves pseudo-random number generation. For instance, in the double-slit experiment we (or some super-natural entity) would need to somehow “program” each particle to follow a different path determined by a different number, which is absurd. However, the present author has no

interest in building a nice deterministic theory compatible with Quantum Mechanics, for the reasons exposed in Section 4. In any case, this explicit example shows unequivocally that the Bell inequalities do not apply to the experiments studying quantum phenomena, because the Bell inequalities depend on assumptions that overlook the fact that time evolution in quantum mechanics is not necessarily a stochastic process.

Note that this deterministic theory is not super-deterministic, i.e. the experimental physicists are free to choose which measurements and which transformations of the state of the system to do [50]. However, an experimental procedure often involves a non-deterministic transformation of the state of the system. Since the non-deterministic transformation in this deterministic theory is reproduced by the pseudo-random number generation, then when we apply the inverse-transform sampling method we need to know already what is the non-deterministic transformation. Thus there is a kind of conspiracy between the non-deterministic transformation and the pseudo-random generator, but such conspiracy is part of the definition of the deterministic transformation itself. There are assumptions about freedom of choice in the literature which exclude our deterministic (but not super-deterministic) theory, because the authors erroneously consider as just a measurement what it is in fact an experimental procedure which involves a transformation of the state of the system [50].

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